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EFFECT OF LASER RE-MELTING PROCESS ON THE MICROSTRUCTURE AND MECHANICAL PROPERTIES OF ADDITIVELY MANUFACTURED METAL MATRIX COMPOSITES

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Background

- Ceramic reinforced Metal Matrix Composites (MMCs)
 - ✓ Combining metal properties (ductility, toughness) with ceramic properties (hardness, thermal stability)
 - ✓ Application in automation, aerospace and military area
- Additive Manufacturing
 - ✓ Flexible in manufacturing
 - ✓ Short period from design to product
- Ti-Ni-C MMCs manufactured via 3D printing
 - Powders used for 3D printing: Ti64 powders and Ni coated graphite particles
 - Laser Engineering Net Shaping (LENS) additive manufacturing system

3D Printing MMCs

LENS MR-7 System

- 4 hopper system
- 500W IPG YLR-500 fibre laser
- Argon atmosphere protection

Re-melting for Residual Carbon Particles Removal

Non Re-melting samples

Re-melting samples

Ti64 with
1.5%C addition

Ti64 with
3.6%C addition

Residual graphite area fractions

Carbon percentage	Non RE-melting	Re-melting
1.5%C	3.16%	2.01%
3.6%C	5.03%	3.33%

- 1/3 residual graphite particles are removed by Re-melting process

Hardness of 3D printed Ti-Ni-C MMCs

- Hardness of the composite are enhanced by the addition of Ni coated graphite
- The hardness improvement can be attributed to the formation of TiC reinforcements
- Re-melting process enhanced the hardness of MMCs
- Hardness increasing of re-melted MMCs is owing to the higher C content which is absorbed in the re-melting process.

Mechanical tests of 3D printed Ti-Ni-C MMCs

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